

Transcription of Interview 6

November 2020

Shane: What is your view of National Health Insurance? It's quite a broad one, but the first thing that comes to your mind.

Interview 6: I think, as a country, we should spend, relatively, a decent amount of money in the provision of healthcare, when you combine private and public health sector. But the discrepancy between the private and the public sector is quite huge; as a country, if we look at the cost of our expenditure on health service provision, I think we can do better. And the NHI is a way to see how we can begin to develop a more equitable system, to ensure that community members, the population at large, have equitable access to health services in our country. Although the vision seems far away, but I think that is the only way we are able to ensure that the general public, especially in the uninsured, may be able to get decent quality care, when you begin to grow a National Health Insurance.

And remember, the National Health Insurance is in the way of when you combine the public and private healthcare sector, is about the pooling of risk, and the funding from both sides, to ensure that more equitable services are provided to all our populations.

And also, it's an endeavour to move towards universal health coverage, for all those who require healthcare; we need to get the appropriate healthcare at the appropriate level they need, at healthcare. I think, currently, sometimes, as we are going forward, although we may have challenges, the access to primary healthcare, especially in the urban areas - I'm not sure in the rural areas - has been improving in the past twenty years. But we need to focus on how we can improve and strengthen primary healthcare service delivery to our population.

But at the current level, access to secondary, tertiary care, is becoming more and more difficult for most of the population. And even us, within the health sector, we're trying to get bookings for our clients who are being referred up for certain investigation, etc.

So I think, to summarise is, the NHI seeks to ensure universal health coverage, so that communities, populations, have equitable access to health services in our country. Over to you, Shane.

Shane: Thanks. And Mr Interview 6, do you think that the NHI is the best way to proceed, in terms of addressing the inequity?

Interview 6: I think many other countries who have developed the NHI model, now, are experiencing some challenges in terms of the funding, in terms of being able to maintain that level of care, which they endeavour to provide. And some of the reasons, especially in the first world, may be due to the fact that they're getting quite a bit of an Asian population, which has resulted in more of the rehab, more of the sort of hospital level care, which needs to be provided for that Asian population.

For us, as a country, we still have a relatively young population, compared to the Northern Hemisphere, and therefore, I think, at this stage, if we are able to pool the funds and develop an efficient system, it can improve, obviously, access to our communities.

The challenge, obviously, is that, how do we begin to make sure that the current services in public sector, especially, and even private sector, to a certain extent, are improved, to meet that standard which will comply with the office of the health standards, so that everyone, wherever they access health services, will have a equitable.. have a level of services, that when they go and seek healthcare at different service points.

[05:27]

I think we can also learn from lessons learnt in the Northern Hemisphere; but I think there are some other countries which have developed a National Health Insurance, which are developing countries; I think, like in Philippines and some of the South Asian countries, they have some sort of an insurance scheme which covers the whole population, whether you can pay or not pay. And so I think we're very fortunate, in the sense that we can learn from lessons learnt in other countries.

But I think the challenge is **in how** we're able to implement the NHI, how we are able to maintain that level of care, and to ensure that our systems are strong enough not to allow abuse of the system. As you know, in the private sector, with the current medical schemes, there's a significant amount of abuse which occurs, and that abuse, obviously, ultimately leads to an increase in cost of private sector service provision. And obviously, the abuse, sometimes, although people may allocate to the public, but I think it takes two to **corrupt**; so I think service providers and the general public, may be responsible for some of the abuse happening in the private medical schemes.

So the challenge is, how we go about putting our systems in place, implementing the NHI, hopefully, progressively, and ensuring, at each step, that things are well-functioning, before we take the next step.

Over to you Shane.

Shane: And Mr Interview 6, you did mention that the NHI is primarily a separate funding scheme, and what are your views on that strategic purchasing, where there's a distinct separation of the funder, as apart from the provider, which would be the public, as well as the private sectors?

Interview 6: So yes, the NHI [...], basically, tries to lay down a framework of how the funding mechanism may work. So I think the challenge would be, as you go forward, is that, do we have adequate capacity in our country? So if the district health management office is the building block, and funds are given to them, remember, the important thing is, will they have the capacity **of skill**, to begin to build adequate strategic, and [...] plans, operational plans, on which, I suppose, funds will be allocated.

The second thing is, remember, our health information system, our epidemiological data, is limited; how do they begin to develop adequate, appropriate plans, on which funding may be allocated; because, obviously, it will be **weighted** against.. it might be per capita, and also against the disease burden. So now if we do not know the disease burden of a particular district, or the sub-district, I always wonder how we're going to **weight for** allocation of funds, if some of the epidemiological data is not available; because in certain areas, the burden may be higher than in another area. So per capita allocation of funds may be oversimplified, to a certain extent. So that's one.

So trying to get appropriate funds, because the district office, then, **after the** issue funds, most probably will be responsible for ensuring that government **begins** to contract out to both public and private sectors. I think the public sector, I think, my understanding, is that it will contract out to the public sector; **if** it is, I'm not sure by facility, or whether it will be by municipality, or the service provider at that local level; **then** to, I suppose, then the private sector, then group practices, may have multidisciplinary practices, or a network of practices, and they need to contract out to them.

[10:31]

So I think, in theory, these contracting units are supposed to have the catchment population. And I think, have we got a relevant.. have we got enough data to be able to determine the catchment population for each contracting unit? Is there an overlap? Well that, I do not, personally, understand completely, because Shane, initially, it would be per capita, but I'm just worried how the funds are going to be utilised **by** the contracting unit **one**.

And then I think, I presume, that also, they may have to buy services from the regional secondary and tertiary hospitals. So how that mechanism is going to work, because they are not part of the district health management system - if I can put it that way – **and then as to whether** we can procure services from those **level**, from the hospital services, or whether the hospitals will have central funds allocated to service in a particular catchment area, I think, is also, not so simple as it sounds.

Currently, remember, many of our hospitals have quite a broad catchment area, so looking at current budgetary allocations, is not a good reflection of what they need, maybe, at a particular service point, or a hospital point.

Did I miss something?

Shane: No. Mr Interview 6, moving on from funding of the NHI, when government originally put forth that they want to implement universal healthcare, how was your experience, in a managerial capacity? Have you had much engagement from government requesting input, or even the channels that you receive information, or developments on the NHI? Can you elaborate, or describe?

Interview 6: Okay, I think, to be fair, I think they initially - because I'm a middle-manager - initially, when some of the debates were occurring, and people were developing policy documents, I think, through the system, there was a request for comments. But most of us in the public sector, are too busy, so I don't think we provided adequate – myself - provided adequate feedback or comments to those who were drafting those policy documents. So that's one. But to say that there was a process where people were asked to comment on many of the things.

But obviously, the Bill itself, went through the formal channels, as a member of the public, you could comment on the Bill. But for some of the other policy documents, there was debates and things like that, long ago. Do you remember? They started ten, fifteen years ago, some of the initial issues. So personally, I did not really participate in that process; but having said that, after some of the policy issues were outlined, obviously, as a middle-manager in the public health sector, we were responsible in trying to implement some of those issues.

Now, the only challenge is, I was working for local government at that stage, so some of these initiatives were implemented through our provincial district office; for example, there were some initial elements, remember, the district clinical specialist teams for maternal health, for **PHC re-engineering**, etc.; so by then, the process started in our district offices, then obviously, those teams supported all services within our district, in **Johannesburg**, for example. So there was no problems in accessing the services, and they did audits in local government, and provincial clinics, or **CHCs**, without any discrimination, also.

[15:17]

Secondly, remember our second principle, of having ward-based outreach teams, like our **WBOT** team, that was also implemented through our provincial offices. So we interacted with this WBOTs, where local government clinics were based, and those WBOT teams, obviously, were based at the local government **clinics**. The challenges with the **WBOT teams**, is that, I think, as a country, although, in the current **DHS**, where **DHS**, some elements have been included, **looking** for the past ten, fifteen years, what we haven't managed to do, is to **draw up** a template, where some of the information being collected by our WBOT teams, is entered, and thereby, becomes much more useful to begin to develop a local community profile. So we're losing some of the main objectives of some of the ward-based outreach teams, by us not being able to capture the information these teams are collecting, so that we can begin to develop a ward-based profile.

And having said that, obviously, they played a really important role in some of the other aspects of **planning**, in terms of improving our health literacy of our communities; helping the services **with** reaching out to defaulters; identifying those who may not have had, as yet, access health services, and to advise them to reach out to the health services, or even take them to the health services; for example, pregnant women, children who may not be immunised, also they identify someone who is **quite unwell**, they facilitate the access to the health services.

So they played an important role, but I think, what we have not done, is optimise their work, because they haven't managed to consolidate onto a platform, all the information they have been collecting over the years. Because I think the main purpose of these outreach teams, is to begin to develop a health profile, and socioeconomic profile, for those communities they are servicing.

Shane: And Mr Interview 6, just continuing with the information, is there a specific channel, or sort of regular communication update, from government, on trajectory and plans for the NHI? Or how do you get most of your news on NHI?

Interview 6: Remember, in the public health sector, we get direct communication for some of the imperatives of building the system, so that you can begin implementation; like for example, as a public health sector, remember, we have this ideal clinic realisation programme, so that you can ensure that we begin to put in appropriate systems, process, and all the necessary equipment, protocols, etc., in place. So I think we get it by default, in a sense, some of the information; so a good example is the ideal clinic, the realisation programme where we're saying how to begin to prepare our primary care services, so that they can meet the **standards** required, how they can comply to the office of the health standards, so that they can get accredited, eventually, when the time comes for accreditation, so that

that unit can become part of the NHI network, also. But otherwise, I think it's public announcements, etc.

Shane: And the information that you say is regularly received, is that to your personal email? Or your government website, is that the main platform?

[20:06]

Interview 6: No, I think, remember, because, with the incrementation now, they get it through policies, through emails, and through directors coming from national or provincial health department.

Shane: Okay. And Mr Interview 6, our third question; what is your perception about the implementation of NHI, in terms of our progress, and the readiness of the public service, and the way forward?

Interview 6: Okay. Shane, just, I've invited one of my colleagues, who's a senior manager, and who's actually directly responsible for NHI implementation services, so she will also answer, she's just joined the meeting now; is that okay?

Shane: That's perfect, yes, that's great.

Interview 6: Ja, okay, so the question is, what are the challenges?

Shane: Ja, or what is the views on the current implementation of the National Health Insurance?

Interview 6: So as I said, firstly, in terms of preparing for the National Health Insurance, like universal health coverage system, government has implemented certain **streams**, right. One is, what I call the ideal clinic realisation stream, where we would like to ensure that each of the public healthcare facility, has [...] processes, systems, equipment, staffing levels, in place; so that is ongoing. And I think, every year, every **round**, so twice a year, we have assessment by the office of the National Health Compliance.. office of the Health Standard Compliance, twice a year. So as local government, or as a district, we try to improve upon every assessment we get.

But some of the key challenges there, is obviously, sometimes equipment is a challenge, especially some of the specialised equipment.

Two, is that many of the facilities, remember, historically, there were some health facilities which were only providing preventive and promotive services, especially in local government. So many of the health facilities have infrastructure challenges, in the sense that they may be a little bit small, to be able to implement all the principles of the ideal clinic, and their shortcomings, in relation to that. But I think, as we go forward, obviously, as budgets do become available an ongoing basis, the health services are trying to **plug those gaps in**.

Thirdly, often, not in some places, often, they have **staffing challenges**. So although there are professional nurses, the challenges, often, is not the number of professional nurses, it's the skills-mix of the professional nurses we have, within the system.

Then, lastly, also, especially in local government, the level of doctor support to each facility, sometimes is a challenge, and sometimes this has **become**, because they're supposed to.. **our** provincial clinics, where they may have **big CHCs**, and therefore, the numbers of facilities may be less, **at** local government, because of the **whole** historical function of preventive and promotive service delivery, they have multiple small, small clinics; you understand?

Shane: Yes.

Interview 6: So the number of service sites is quite high, and therefore, sometimes, ensuring that there's adequate doctor support for all our service points, sometimes can be a challenge. And I think, in terms of staffing, **until**, as government, we don't begin to have – if I can call it – one public service, then we're going to have staffing challenges, where staff will jump from one authority to another authority, like from provincial service to local government, or from local government to provincial services. So if we are going to begin to move towards NHI, one important component we must address, fully enough, is that there's one conditions of service for all public sector health personnel.

[25:01]

So I think, for years, the government has been talking about one public service, but we haven't moved towards it; but if **there's** any **change**, especially in the health sector, we need to begin to talk to it, and then begin to sort it out, to minimise this jumping of staff, from one service to another service.

Shane: And Mr Interview 6, you mentioned the solutions, and the one is the staffing and having a unified public health service; you also mentioned the epidemiological data.

Interview 6: Okay, ja. What I'm saying, is, part of the planning, strategic and operational, the annual plans, on which, sometimes the funding we develop, may be allocated against the plans submitted. So I'm saying we were worried about the completeness – I won't say quality - the completeness of those plans, in the **absence** of country - not only Johannesburg – country, not having adequate local level epidemiological data.

I think, remember, throughout the country, especially in the public health sector, and even in the private health sector, very few people have a **pension**-based data, from which we can derive the health profiles of a particular community. So often, we have aggregate data, which sometimes, especially in the public sector, we do track certain important priority conditions, but we do not necessarily track all the conditions; even when you talk about NCDs, non-communicable diseases, sometimes there are some elements which we track, in terms of the routine, **DHIS**, but that does not give us indication of, say, the of some of these very common NCDs in our communities, also.

So **still**, we don't have the patient-base of records, from which we can aggregate profiles for certain communities, catchment population, then it's difficult to begin to develop an adequate strategic plan, or a operational plan, so that there's adequate funds, or appropriate amount of funds allocated, for the disease burden for that particular community; so I think it's in that context.

But also, for planning purposes, you need to know the profile, we know if the chronic disease burden is high, I mean, the chronic disease burden is not once-off, compared to acute **illnesses**, and therefore, in

terms of service delivery, the burden on the services will be much greater in that particular catchment, or that particular area, compared to another area where there might be a younger population, and then majority of the service needs may be for acute illnesses, or injuries, and some of the preventive, promotive services.

Shane: Ja. Okay then, Mr Interview 6, that's the bulk of my questions. Is there any other view or thought, around NHI, that you would like to express?

Interview 6: So I think, remember, that the Bill also talks to having a uniform National Health Information System. So I'm not too sure, I haven't looked at the detail, but hopefully, there'll be one information system, which the whole NHI will work from; and hopefully, that information system would begin to have individual patient profiles, so that as we begin to build a system, we are able to get a more complete health profile of a particular community which we are trying to service, also. So I think some of the system issues become important as we go forward, isn't it?

Shane: Yes.

Interview 6: But apart from making sure that the services are complied to, the officer of the health standards comply it; but in addition to that, we need to make sure that other systems are in place, like also in terms of procurement of equipment, etc., so that everyone are.. so, [...], especially the public sector, they are using equipment which complies, which are adequate for the work we have to do for that particular community.

[30:00]

Shane: Okay.

Interview 6: Okay, the other issue is, as we go forward, I think - I'm not sure, I haven't read up everything - is that, how do we ensure that the competency of the health workers, doctors, nurses, and all the other health workers, pharmacists, physios, special.. the training or continuous professional development of these health workers, become important, to ensure that people are up-to-date with the latest developments, and they are able to manage appropriately.

But secondly, also, obviously, that I think, I know in the NHS in the UK, they have standard protocols, so for hospital level and for primarily healthcare level, I know they talk about STGs at the hospital level, and standard treatment guidelines for provincial level, to minimise over-treatment or under-treatment of clients, who are attending that particular service point. So there's about skills level, continuous professional development, uniform guidelines, at all levels, so we all have the same standard of care - I can say - that needs to be developed also, and those guidelines need to be imparted to all health workers.

Shane: Okay then, Mr Interview 6, thanks so much for your time; that's all from my side. As soon as I can, I'll get the audio onto a Word document, and then just send that back, that you could have a look at, and see if you approve, or if anything you'd want to change.

Interview 6: Okay, thank you. Okay, Shane, bye.

Shane: Ja, thanks again. Have a good day. Bye.

-----oO-----